

Fuzziness and Wobbliness in Numismatics and Ceramology: Examples from the NFDI4Objects Knowledge Graph

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ABSTRACT

Archaeological data is inherently characterised by vagueness and uncertainty, we use the terms "fuzziness" and "wobbliness" in order to acknowledge that a clear border, reason or source is often missing. In addition, traditional systems often fail to adequately represent it. This paper, developed within the NFDI4Objects consortium's TRAIL 2.2, presents approaches to model and manage such ambiguous information within numismatics and ceramology.

In the field of numismatics, the Antike Fundmünzen Europa (AFE) serves as example, demonstrating the capacity to record and represent varying degrees of fuzziness and wobbliness in human-entered data. The paper briefly looks at different Linked Open Data (LOD) modelling strategies for uncertainty, comparing reification (statements about a statement) with a proposed extra node approach, emphasizing pitfalls related to SPARQL queries and transitive properties. One solution we are proposing in order to make usage having fuzziness and wobbliness captured is the Uncertainty Reasoner, which employs Dempster-Shafer theory to combine human input, domain knowledge, and AI confidence levels. This approach explicitly accounts for ignorance, thereby offering more nuanced interpretations.

In the domain of ceramology, the Academic Meta Tool (AMT) employs a semantic modelling approach that utilizes weighted edges to articulate ambiguous relations within ceramic datasets. This methodology has been exemplified through an analysis of Samian Ware. The initiative's objective is to incorporate these disparate modelling strategies into NFDI4Objects overarching semantic framework, encompassing OCMDP and MaChECo, with the aim of ensuring interoperability and adherence to the FAIR principles. The work's primary objective is to raise awareness about the management of uncertain and unreliable data. It advocates for a standardized approach and underscores the significance of expert oversight, particularly in the context of incorporating AI-generated likelihoods.

Keywords: Uncertainty, Vagueness, Fuzziness and Wobbliness, Linked Open Data (LOD), Dempster-Shafer theory

Introduction

The concepts of vagueness and uncertainty can be found anywhere in archaeology. Vague statements per se are certain, e.g., the object A is dated between 100 and 200 AD. Nothing is uncertain about it (as far as we can see here). In case the dating of object A represents the production date of a coin or a ceramic vessel (produced within a very short time), a range of 100 years is vague. The preservation status of the object might only allow an approximation. In this case, the expressed vagueness is due to uncertainty. It could also be that whoever stated the statement was not interested in the exact dating, and his range reflects the granularity he needed for his research question. Our understanding is that the habits and best practices in the various disciplines can also change over time. This already illustrates that we are confronted with a rather huge problem. Identifying the situation and understanding why uncertain or vague information is given is already a challenge in itself. We use the terms fuzziness and wobbliness to reflect that these concepts of vagueness and uncertainty, which could be distinguished in theory, overlap in many practical cases.

Unfortunately, many systems do not allow the entry and representation of uncertain or vague information. In case you have just one entry possibility, the entering person needs to decide what to choose. In pure text fields, people often use question marks or other ways to indicate such cases. With a more structured way of entering information and the usage of existing norm data like provided by Nomisma.org for numismatics, these possibilities disappeared. The clearer structure and usage of norm data however is important to use, combine and query the data. In the section about numismatics we will show with an example of Antike Fundmünzen Europa (AFE)¹ that such a clear structure is not in contradiction to the possibility to model and store fuzziness and wobbliness. Of course, it makes things more complicated and mapping this into Linked Open Data (LOD) is another issue to discuss. However, reality is not binary. In the section on numismatics we will show the usage of Dempster-Shafer theory also referred to as evidence theory (Dempster 1967, Shafer 1976). This will illustrate the potential even to add additional information that was not entered but still could be an option due to other knowledge sources. This approach is also capable of handling different inputs from different sources, like combining the human-entered information with others or even with one or multiple AI model results. In the end, such an approach generates quite some probabilities, and one could argue that this is confusing. However, looking at the usage of large language models that are based on probabilities and are increasingly used, it might be worth a try.

¹ Information about AFE and its instances: <http://www.bigdata.uni-frankfurt.de/afe-web/> (all links last accessed 10.09.2025)

Before digging into our numismatic and ceramic use cases and approaches in those fields, we will provide a short introduction into NFDI4Objects we are part of. Finally, the paper closes with a recapitulation and outlook.

NFDI4Objects

The NFDI4Objects consortium, part of Germany's National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) initiative (Thiery, Mees, Weisser, et al. 2023; Rummel et al. 2025; Thiery et al. 2025), encompasses a broad scholarly community focused on studying material remains spanning approximately 2.6 million years of human history. It draws from various disciplines, including the humanities, cultural studies, and natural sciences, emphasising archaeological and historical research. Objects and their associated relationships are dynamic, undergoing transformations reflecting their life cycles through documentation, collection, analysis, preservation, storage, and dissemination processes (Thiery, Mees, Weisser, et al. 2023). One of NFDI4Objects' goals is to create and publish interlinked LOD within the interdisciplinary federated Knowledge Graph Ecosystem (Fig. 1) – consisting of Linked Open Data (Schmidt et al. 2022; Thiery and Thiery 2023), Wikibases and FAIR Digital Objects – to make archaeological data interoperable with neighbouring domains (Rossenova et al. 2025).

Figure 1 - A distributed Knowledge Graph Scheme bringing together Linked Open Data and FAIR Digital Objects approaches. Florian Thiery & Andreas Noback, CC BY 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons.

Within a so-called TRAIL (Task Related Activities for Implementation and Launch of Services) – 2.2: Evaluation of fuzziness and wobbliness in numismatics and ceramology (Thiery et al. 2021) – within NFDI4Objects, the authors of this paper intend to collect and represent use cases from those two domains. The goal is to drill down into some of them and to explore them in more detail.

In the context of TRAIL 2.2 and within this paper, we will present some of the use cases from Numismatics and Ceramology and possibilities to entail new information from them. Most of the current data in both disciplines is generated by humans. This means experts look at the object and, based on expertise (and sometimes mood or depending on many other things), enter the information about it into a database. Asking experts to include a likelihood value of how sure their assessment is would (a) cost quite some time, (b) raise the question of what a likelihood of 53% exactly means, and (c) vary depending on the current circumstances. Since we are now in a phase in which information is also entered by AI systems that (depending on the system) can provide a likelihood value that can at least be reproduced in case the model stays stable. It becomes important to (a) understand the potential for having the exact likelihood values of Machine Learning (ML) Systems including Artificial Intelligence (AI) models and (b) indicate what needs to be stored as additional context information to avoid problems later. Based on such given likelihoods, reasoners can be used to entail new triples with an accordingly calculated likelihood for them (Weigel 2024).

Within our use cases, we intend to show the potential, compare different approaches and lay the ground for future decisions. This includes the following questions: (a) What is important to store? (b) What are possible ways to model it? and (c) What can be achieved by making this effort? Since we are in a transition phase (as things are constantly changing), the combination of data modelled without such details also needs to be addressed.

Numismatics

We would like to present use cases from the database Ancient Find Coins in Europe (AFE) based on Roman Imperial coins. For those cases each coin is attributed to exactly one issuer (emperor) and optionally one person can be specified the coin was issued for (in honour of), represented by the portrait on the obverse. This means both fields can have only one exact value. However, since AFE focuses on coin finds (that are often not so well preserved), the system allows different entry options to represent the uncertainty and vagueness of the person entering the data about the given coin. The use cases presented herein are restricted to these two interconnected and significant fields, in order to minimise complexity. It is evident that entries in these fields would also have implications for other fields, such as the dating of the coin. The existence of such interrelations between fields are sometimes obvious, sometimes they depend on additional context and deeper domain knowledge.

Fig. 2 below shows the section to enter this information in the AFE entry form. First, the portrait can be entered (this is mainly for Roman coins the head of the person on the obverse side – for other fields of numismatics this is less relevant), since this is normally the first information a numismatist would recognise when analysing a Roman coin. Afterwards the issuer can be entered. Both fields allow the specification of alternatives, one alternative for issuing for and two alternatives for the issuer. In case more than one issuer

or issuing for person is entered, this means the numismatist that analyses the coin is not sure which of the persons is the correct one. However, the numismatist is certain that one of the two entered persons is the correct one. Such an entry would represent in our definition a vague entry. On the right side of the form it is also possible to check the uncertain flag. If this is activated, it means that the provided information is uncertain and other (not entered) values could also be true.

Issuing for	<input type="text"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> uncertain
Issuing for alternative	<input type="text"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Issuer	<input type="text"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> uncertain
Issuer alternative 1	<input type="text"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Issuer alternative 2	<input type="text"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	

Figure 2 – Part of the entry form to enter coins into Antike Fundmünzen Europa (AFE). Issuing for represents the portrayed person on the obverse side and the issuer administratively responsible for the issue of the coin. Both entries allow alternatives (only one can be valid) and in addition the possibility to say that the entering person is uncertain about entered value(s).

All together this allows the following options/cases for the entering of some fields in AFE:

1. One value is entered and the entering person is certain about this (certain statement).
2. One value is entered and the entering person is NOT certain about this (uncertain statement).
3. More than one value is entered and the entering person is certain one of these values is correct (vague statement).
4. More than one value is entered and the entering person is NOT certain if one of these values is correct (vague and uncertain statement).

Besides the shown fields in Fig. 2, AFE provides these alternative options additionally only for the entry of mint and denomination of a coin. In order to avoid a too extensive entry form, all other fields only allow one entry and provide the option to mark the entered information as uncertain. In our experience these alternative options for some of the core fields in fact can reduce the time to enter coins. If only one option is available, the entering person needs to invest time and effort in order to decide which one to choose. On top there are situations that simply do not allow to narrow it down to one value. Having the opportunity to add alternatives therefore better reflects the reality or at least the opinion of the person providing the data. Due to dependencies between entry fields, it must be stressed that allowing different options can also cause extra complexity. For example for plausibility checks in order keep track of the data quality. Another restriction would be the dating field in AFE, which currently permits only a single time interval. Allowing different options, e.g. for the issuer, could also be implemented in a way that assigns values for

other fields that are connected directly with these fields. Those trade-offs between precision and simplicity of the input forms may also be subject to change over time.

When exchanging information as LOD there are already (different) ways to model uncertain information or possible alternatives. However, this is not standardized and therefore in many cases such information is either ignored (meaning it is exported as certain data) or completely neglected. Both are not optimal! This is exactly what our trail in NFDI4O is working on and we want to provide solutions.

Numismatics - Modelling uncertainty in Linked Open Data

Different approaches to modelling uncertain information in Linked Open Data (LOD), more precisely in the Resource Description Framework (RDF), are already discussed in (Tolle and Wigg-Wolf 2014). A more comprehensive overview is provided in (Sabah and Sabah 2022). A dedicated tool called RDFier for generating RDF based on different approaches is presented in (Pöpperl 2023). RDFier operates on CSV input data and supports the selection of different RDF modelling approaches, including RDF-Star ('RDF & SPARQL Working Group Charter', n.d.). RDF-Star extends the original RDF standard of using triples by adding an additional level (quadruples e.g. to express reification - statements about a statement). However, in this paper we concentrate on triple based solutions.

Our first use case for uncertain entries in Fig. 3 can be expressed as: There is a coin (afe:12365²) and the issuer of that coin is Augustus, but the entering person is not certain about this statement. By using Nomisma.org ontology³ for this situation one can use the property "nmo:hasIssuer" and the norm data representation of Augustus from the Nomisma.org ID space⁴ "nm:augustus".

Figure 3 – Translation of the entered data into RDF triples (without uncertainty).

² Public link to AFE coin 12365: <http://afe.dainst.org/coin?afeid=12365>

³ Nomisma.org ontology: <http://nomisma.org/ontology#>

⁴ Nomisma.org id namespace: <https://nomisma.org/id/>

As a CSV-file for RDFier (including uncertainty using a W3C UncertaintyOntology⁵ property) this would look like:

```
coin^^uri,nmo:hasIssuer^^uri**1,1__un:hasUncertainty^^certainty
afe:12365,nm:augustus,u
```

In RDFier the user can select a representation style for that uncertain entry. Fig. 4 shows a style that was used by the British museum and Fig. 5 shows the style we propose also in the context of Nomisma.org.

Figure 4 – Translation of the entered data into RDF triples with uncertainty using a reification approach as used to be in a British museum approach. That contains the triple: afe:12365, nmo:hasIssuer, nm:augustus without uncertainty.

Figure 5 – Translation of the entered data into RDF triples using a blank node (without a global URI) as information carrier and this way not containing the triple: afe:12365, nmo:hasIssuer, nm:augustus without uncertainty.

The first version basically uses a kind of reification, where the triple: afe:12365, nmo:hasIssuer, nm:augustus without uncertainty is included within the graph and you build something around it representing this statement and finally state that it is uncertain (nm:uncertain_value). The second approach does not contain the statement as such, it basically replaces the original object of the triple with an extra node and connects an uncertain value node and the information about this uncertainty to it, in

⁵ W3C Uncertainty Ontology: <https://www.w3.org/2005/Incubator/urw3/wiki/UncertaintyOntology.html>

this case just saying it is uncertain (nm:uncertain_value), but it could also be indicated as percentage. In Fig. 5 a blank node (without a global URI) is used, however, a node with a provided URI could also be used and would allow referencing, e.g. allowing others to comment it.

As mentioned, there are also other ways to model it. However, in our view the existence of the statement that is uncertain within the graph does have implications and it is important to highlight them in order to avoid pitfalls. The main two pitfalls in those situations are:

1. SPARQL queries can simply return the statement without the context information that it is in fact uncertain. This might lead to wrong assumptions. E.g. the query:

```
SELECT ?coin ?issuer WHERE { ?coin nmo:hasIssuer ?issuer }
```

would simply return: `afe:12365 nm:augustus` for Fig. 4 and this information could be taken for granted. For Fig. 5 it would return: `afe:12365 _a:3` (`_a:3` is a representation for a blank node that could vary depending on the system you use). The blank node information would force the user to request more information with another query and this way he can learn that the provided information under `rdf:value: nm:augustus` is uncertain.

2. Additionally, we can have the situation that the used property could for example be a transitive property (element of `owl:TransitiveProperty`⁶). In those cases the entailment of a reasoner would continue and might generate additional statements based on uncertain data. In some cases this might be on purpose, in others one probably would like to avoid this.

However, the classical reification that includes the statement that is then marked as uncertain, is widely used and supported. For RDF-Star for example a translation using reified statements is available ('RDF-Star and SPARQL-Star', n.d.). The goals of our efforts in NFDI are to highlight possible problems and try to reduce the number of used existing representations or at least to avoid the generation of new ones.

Numismatics – Using the numbers ... what are the benefits?

Jens Weigel generated in his master's thesis (Weigel 2024) a reasoner (called Uncertainty Reasoner) that is able to calculate with uncertainties. His approach has been further developed by Oussama Izelgue (Izelgue 2025). In order to do reasoning likelihoods need to be provided. Their implementation therefore also allows the assignment of the likelihood values in case they are not included (called CertaintyAssignmentAxiom). In cases data is entered into the system by humans like in AFE, default values are used to indicate that an uncertainty flag is marked or alternatives are provided. It needs to be stressed that in case an IT system like an ML model provides information, its own confidence level could and should be used instead of such default values. In the following we will present a walkthrough of an example describing the results of the DempsterShaferAxiom implemented inside the reasoner that is based

⁶ `owl:TransitiveProperty` a `rdfs:Class`: <https://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#TransitiveProperty>

on the Dempster-Shafer theory (DST) (Dempster 1967; Shafer 1976; Sentz and Ferson 2002). The DST can be viewed as an extension of the Bayesian theory that allows a level of ignorance (also called uncommitted belief). Ignorance in this context allows us to specify to what extent other possibilities than those listed as hypotheses could be true, due to the lack of evidence. For example, if you have a very corroded coin and you assume the head shown on one side is either Augustus or Tiberius, but it could also be another person. In this case you can provide a likelihood to both Augustus and Tiberius and you can use the remaining likelihood to sum up to 100% and put it into the ignorance, e.g. Augustus 50%, Tiberius 30% and ignorance 20%. There are also other approaches for uncertainty reasoning (Smith 1990; Guo et al. 2024). We selected DST mainly because of its explicit usage of ignorance (not true for all approaches) and due its high-level of awareness.

Let us start with the situation illustrated in Fig. 6 below. The user who entered the information is certain about Tiberius being shown on the obverse side of the coin and he thinks (but is uncertain about) that the coin was issued under Augustus. The reasoner internally reflects this situation in a table representation, including the domain knowledge shown as possible issuers in case the head of Tiberius is depicted on the obverse side. Domain knowledge is knowledge which is already stored in the database (in a separate table) and was generated by a numismatist. This representation is mainly the original RDF representation consisting of the subject, predicate and object information but without certainty/uncertainty as shown already in Fig 3. The table additionally has a separate certainty column. Since no certainties are provided (human entry), this last column needs to be filled by applying the CertaintyAssignmentAxiom. Currently we are using the value of 20% as default for cases the user marked an entry as uncertain (since the Uncertainty Reasoner is implemented in Python, one could simply provide a different value if wanted to change this, link see Data, Scripts... section at the end). This value generated good results in tests for our examples and use cases. Before finally applying the DempsterShaferAxiom for the shown case the table would look like shown in Table 1.

Issuing for	<input type="text" value="Tiberius (Tiberius)"/> ✖ Possible Issuers: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Augustus (Augustus) • Tiberius (Tiberius) 	<input type="checkbox"/> uncertain
Issuing for alternative	<input type="text"/> ✖	
Issuer	<input type="text" value="Augustus (Augustus)"/> ✖	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> uncertain

Figure 6 – Cut-out of the AFE form to enter coins with the values for the example. Tiberius is entered as Issuing for. Once entered the system shows possible issuers based on the internal defined domain knowledge. The user in this case entered Augustus as issuer and marked it as uncertain.

Table 1 – The translation of the entered information in fig. 6 and the belief values based on default values of the uncertainty reasoner (0.2 for the uncertain flag) after executing the CertaintyAssignmentAxiom.

subject	predicate	object	certainty
afe:12365	nmo:hasIssuer	nm:augustus	0.8
afe:12365	nmo:hasIssuer	uncertain	0.2
afe:12365	nmo:hasPortrait	nm:tiberius	1
nm:tiberius	ex:hasPossibleIssuer	nm:augustus	0.5
nm:tiberius	ex:hasPossibleIssuer	nm:tiberius	0.5

In case the DempsterShaferAxiom is now called for the “nmo:hasIssuer” property taking “nmo:hasPortrait” and the domain knowledge “ex:hasPossibleIssuer” into account. As possible values for the property “nmo:hasIssuer”, we would have of course “nm:augustus” as entered by the user. Additionally, based on the domain knowledge also “nm:tiberius” would be a possible candidate. Finally, the ignorance is provided by the Dempster-Shafer theory. Therefore, we have three options and two so-called mass functions (representing the likelihood values from the user and based on the domain knowledge) as shown in Table 2. For the ignorance again 20% are used as a default value. The domain knowledge (not including uncertainty) therefore has 20% for ignorance and distributes the remaining 80% equally to both other cases. The human entered situation only has one value but since it is marked as uncertain, it gets an ignorance of 40% (20% + 20%) and the remaining 60% for the entered Augustus and 0% for Tiberius. The result of the combined mass function for the Dempster-Shafer theory is also shown in Table 2.

Table 2 – Resulting input mass functions for the user and based on the domain knowledge for each possibility together with the combined mass function as result of the DempsterShaferAxiom.

possibilities A	user mass function (m_u)	domain knowledge mass function (m_d)	combined mass function ($m_{ud}(A)$)
nm:augustus	0.6	0.4	0.684
nm:tiberius	0	0.4	0.211
ignorance	0.4	0.2	0.105

The values of the combined mass function show that the combination of both reduces ignorance dramatically. As compensation “nm:tiberius” would now also be listed as “nmo:hasIssuer” with a likelihood of 21.1%. This allows researchers to avoid neglecting alternative possibilities that might not be seen as those during entry (domain knowledge might change over time) or just had not been seen by the person who entered it. Alternatively, it can help for cases where the GUI did not allow them to enter alternatives. Since the issuer entered by the user was also part of the domain knowledge mass function, his probability was even increased compared to the user mass function.

Here a small mathematical explanation how the numbers for the combined mass function are calculated. The formula for it is:

$$m_{ud}(A) = \frac{1}{1-K} \sum_{X \cap Y = A} m_u(X)m_d(Y) \quad \text{with conflict } K = \sum_{X \cap Y = \emptyset} m_u(X)m_d(Y)$$

We need to consider all pairs (X,Y) with X from the user and Y from the domain. X and Y are both: {nm:augustus, nm:tiberius, ignorance}. This results in nine pairs. Each pair with ignorance is not defined as empty, since it is either the ignorance itself or the result would be the non-ignorance value. E.g. X = {nm:augustus} and Y = {ignorance} would mean that $X \cap Y = \text{nm:augustus}$. When we look at the conflict K, these are the cases where X and Y have no overlapping opinion, mathematically expressed as $X \cap Y = \emptyset$. By checking all nine pairs, this results in two pairs with conflict, X = {nm:augustus} Y = {nm:tiberius} and the other way round X = {nm:tiberius} Y = {nm:augustus}. Since the belief value for $m_u(\{\text{nm:tiberius}\})$ is zero, this pair can be ignored, with the multiplication with zero it would have no contribution to the sum. K in this case can therefore be calculated with just one pair:

$$K = m_u(\{\text{nm: augustus}\}) \times m_d(\{\text{nm: tiberius}\}) = 0.6 \times 0.4 = 0.24$$

At the end $1-K = 1-0.24 = 0.76$ becomes the normalizing value the sum afterwards is divided with. To calculate now the sum for example for A = nm:augustus, one would have the cases $X \cap Y = A$. This would be the case if both say nm:augustus or if one side uses nm:augustus and the other ignorance, resulting in three summand:

1. $m_u(\{\text{nm: augustus}\}) \times m_d(\{\text{nm: augustus}\}) = 0.6 \times 0.4 = 0.24$
2. $m_u(\{\text{nm: augustus}\}) \times m_d(\{\text{ignorance}\}) = 0.6 \times 0.2 = 0.12$
3. $m_u(\{\text{ignorance}\}) \times m_d(\{\text{nm: augustus}\}) = 0.4 \times 0.4 = 0.16$

$$\text{The sum would be: } 0.24 + 0.12 + 0.16 = 0.52 \text{ and } m_{ud}(\{\text{nm: augustus}\}) = \frac{0.52}{0.76} \approx 0.684 .$$

The resulting mass function sums up to 100% again. This is because each input mass function adds up to 100%. When we would therefore calculate the Cartesian product (sum of each value of one side multiplied with each value of the other side) one would get 100% again. This Cartesian product is basically done in the second sum for cases without conflict (let us call this J). The Dempster-Shafer theory ignores these conflict cases and normalizes the result accordingly by calculating K. The sum of K and J would be 100%. This means $1-K = J$ and therefore when you sum over the combined mass function you end up with 100% again.

To sum up, this means that different opinions and options from different experts, AI models or provided domain knowledge as in our case can be combined. The ignorance introduced by the Dempster-Shafer theory on top can provide a useful approach to rate your data compared to the confidence level of AI systems.

Ceramology: Use Case from Samian Research

Alongside numismatics, ceramics – in particular Samian Ware – represent a classic case of “fuzzy” or “wobbly” data in archaeology (Thiery and Mees 2018). In this context, the Academic Meta Tool (AMT)

provides a semantic modelling approach that enables vague relations within ceramic datasets to be expressed in a structured and computationally usable way (Unold et al. 2019). In a dedicated use case (Thiery et al. 2022), the Samian Research database and its LOD counterpart, Linked Open Samian Ware (Thiery, Mees, and Kiesling 2023; Thiery 2024; Thiery et al. 2020) were used, comprising over 7.8 million RDF triples and more than 300,000 instances, published under an open DPPL licence. Within this dataset, approximately 21% of entries contain vague or uncertain information, typically signalled by string expressions including the keywords AND, OR, or the use of a question mark. Two examples may illustrate these challenges and the AMT approach:

- Example A (Potters and kiln sites): The potter Quietus is attributed to both `Rheinzabern AND Krähenwald ?`. Within AMT this results in a connection degree of 0.5 for Rheinzabern, reflecting the fact that his career began there before moving on to Krähenwald, however the question mark indicates a uncertainty decreasing the weight
- Example B (Vessel fragments): A potsherd (Information Carrier 118117) is associated with multiple possible Dragendorff forms (`18 OR 15/17 OR 18/31`). This vagueness is expressed in AMT by assigning a connection degree of 0.33 to form 18, reflecting one out of three possible alternatives, cf. Fig. 7, where samian:pf_9 is Dragendorff 18.
- The AMT modelling strategy can be extended to further attribute dimensions, such as decorative motifs, fabric classifications, workshop attributions, or chronological ranges, provided that transparent transformation rules from textual encodings to semantic relations are defined (Thiery and Mees 2025; Mees and Thiery 2026).

Technically, AMT constructs a semantically modelled knowledge network using concept nodes and weighted edges that represent a normalised degree of connection between 0 and 1 (Fig. 8). Formally, the transformation from textual ambiguity to graded semantic relations follows explicit rule-based normalisation procedures. In cases of mutually exclusive alternatives of question marks and possibilities (concatenated with OR or AND) the weight (degree of connection) is calculated as:

$$w = \frac{1}{n_{questionmarks} + n_{possibilities}}$$

with the assumptions: (i) no AND/OR: total count of possibilities for all entities = 1; (ii) AND: total count of possibilities for all entities = 1; (iii) OR: total count of possibilities is the count of entities between the OR statements. Here, $n_{possibilities}$ denotes the number of alternative attributions encoded in the string, while $n_{questionmarks}$ captures explicitly marked uncertainty indicators, both contributing to a normalised degree of semantic applicability (Thiery et al., 2022).

Under equal interpretation, an expression such as “18 OR 15/17 OR 18/31” therefore results in $w = 0.33$ for each alternative. These weights do not represent statistical probabilities but degrees of semantic applicability (Unold et al. 2019). These weighted relations are defined within a meta-ontology, from which a domain-specific ontology can be generated. By applying role-chain axioms and multivalued logics, the

approach allows reasoning across uncertain or vague statements in a way that goes beyond conventional triple-based RDF modelling. However, the assignment of connection degrees depends on explicitly documented and community-agreed interpretation rules and therefore introduces a controlled degree of subjectivity. The Samian use case has further been integrated into Linked Open Samian Ware, aligned with CIDOC CRM to be compatible with the CIDOC CRM based NFDI4Objects Knowledge Graph⁷.

These semantic enrichments ensure interoperability and compliance with the FAIR principles. Within TRAIL 2.2 of NFDI4Objects, the Samian example complements the numismatic case study, demonstrating how different modelling strategies for vagueness and uncertainty can be made interoperable and exchangeable into a broader research infrastructure. While the numismatic use case models epistemic uncertainty through evidential belief combination (DST), the ceramic case formalises semantic vagueness as graded conceptual relations. Both approaches address non-binary archaeological evidence but operate on different layers of imperfection, uncertainty versus vagueness. Their coexistence within the same research infrastructure demonstrates that heterogeneous modelling strategies can be integrated without conceptual conflict.

Figure 7 - Exemplary schematic representation of Samian Ware potforms as AMT modelling. Florian Thiery & Allard W. Mees, CC BY 4.0.

⁷ cf. <https://graph.nfdi4objects.net>

Figure 8 - Exemplary schematic representation of the AMT model. Florian Thiery & Martin Unold, CC BY 4.0.

NFDI4Objects - MaChEco & OCMDP

A significant challenge for TRAIL 2.2 will be integrating the different concepts of fuzzy and wobbly data modelling into the Object Core Metadata Profile (OCMDP) and the Material Cultural Heritage Crosswalk Ontology (MaChEco), which together aim to provide a common semantic framework for interoperability across NFDI from NFDI4Objects as a basis. The OCMDP defines a shared metadata profile aligned with international standards (e.g. schema.org, DCAT, DataCite), while MaChEco establishes hierarchical ontology crosswalks to CIDOC CRM. For these models to fully support archaeological practice, they must be able to capture community-agreed ways of expressing vagueness and uncertainty. By feeding such standards into MaChEco, fuzzy and wobbly information from disciplines like numismatics and ceramology can be consistently represented and made FAIR within the NFDI4Objects Knowledge Graph.

In this context, the numismatic DST-based modelling and the ceramic AMT-based modelling operate on different layers of epistemic imperfection. While DST combines evidential uncertainty at the level of competing hypotheses, AMT encodes semantic vagueness as graded relations between concepts. MaChEco does not collapse these approaches into a single formalism but provides a crosswalk layer in which both uncertainty statements and graded relations can be described within a shared CIDOC CRM-aligned framework. This allows heterogeneous modelling strategies to coexist while remaining interoperable within the NFDI4Objects Knowledge Graph.

Discussion and outlook

Many systems still do not allow the storage or entry of vague or uncertain data. However, reality is not binary, especially in the domain of archaeology. We are mainly facing a chicken-and-egg dilemma to some extent. Since many systems do not allow such entries, there is also no real need to model it. Therefore, the need to agree on a modelling standard within LOD is also not so high on people's agenda.

However, the challenge to handle fuzzy and wobbly information is huge. It is even listed under the remaining challenge for the Semantic Web in Wikipedia⁸. With our presented approaches and implementations like the Uncertainty Reasoner and the AMT tool, we hope to show some opportunities but also pitfalls in a step forward. Together, these approaches demonstrate complementary strategies for addressing epistemic uncertainty (DST) and semantic vagueness (AMT) within graph-based infrastructures. By an active usage of ignorance in DST we also tried to demonstrate that such approaches allow some flexibilities, also in respect of wrongly entered information. In addition the understanding and documentation of relationships and dependencies between fields like issuer and portrait person on the coin would be useful, especially for less obvious cases. Such information can be used for uncertainty reasoning as we do. In addition, simple rule based systems can also build on top in order to find conflicting data entries and this way increase data quality in archaeological databases.

Future work within NFDI4Objects will focus on embedding such modelling strategies explicitly into MaChECo and OCMDP profiles, thereby transforming domain-specific uncertainty practices into interoperable and reusable semantic standards. Providing and publishing such modelling strategies is a mandatory step forward to break the mentioned chicken-and-egg dilemma.

Especially due to the current boost in ML, it is important to represent reality as accurately as possible in the data. Many of such systems do provide confidence levels as outputs of the models and we encourage everybody to store such information. This information can be the basis for uncertainty reasoning approaches that can help to combine results of different systems in order to improve them. It must be stressed that if an AI system hallucinates, it might also have a high confidence level for its answer, even if a human expert would immediately recognise the error. It is therefore important to keep the experts in the loop!

Data, scripts, code, and supplementary information availability

Uncertainty Reasoner by Jens Weigel : <https://github.com/jensw99/uncertainty-reasoner>

Extension of the Uncertainty Reasoner by Oussama Izelgue : <https://github.com/Oussama-Izg/uncertainty-reasoner>

⁸ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Semantic_Web

RDFier by Jan Luca Pöpperl to generate RDF based on CSV files including different modelling approaches for uncertainty in RDF:

- Github repository: <https://github.com/poepperl/rdfier>
- Web App: <https://rdfier.streamlit.app/>

Academic Meta Tool (AMT):

- AMT vocabulary description: <https://academic-meta-tool.xyz/vocab/>
- AMT ontology description: <https://academic-meta-tool.xyz/ontology/>
- AMT ontology: <https://github.com/mainzed/academicmetatool-ontology>
- Web App for testing: <https://github.com/leiza-rse/amt-playground>

Conflict of interest disclosure

The authors declare that they comply with the PCI rule of having no financial conflicts of interest in relation to the content of the article.

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